

Use of azine dye as photosensitizer in solar cell. NTA-safranine system

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Manuscript received 3 November 1999, accepted 9 March 2000

Photogalvanic effect has been studied in photogalvanic cell containing safranine and NTA as photosensitizer and reductant, respectively. The photopotential and photocurrent generated by the system are 415 mV and 35 μ A, respectively. The effects of different parameters on electrical output of the cell are observed and a mechanism has been proposed.

Some interesting photogalvanic systems have been reported in the literature^{1,2}. Various problems encountered in this field have also been discussed³. Theoretical conversion efficiency of photogalvanic cell is about 18% but the observed conversion efficiencies are quite low due to lower stability of dyes, back-electron transfer, aggregation of dye molecules around electrode, etc. The literature reveals the use of different photosensitizers in photogalvanic cells, e.g. riboflavin, brilliant cresyl blue, methylene blue, toluidine blue and azur C, but no attention has been paid to the use of azine dye as photosensitizer in photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion. Hence, the present work was undertaken by selecting NTA-safranine system for this purpose.

Table 1. Effect of variation of pH

[Saf] = 4.00×10^{-6} M, [NTA] = 2.00×10^{-2} M, Temp = 303 K,
Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}

	pH				
	12.0	12.4	12.6	12.9	13.0
Photopotential (mV)	222.0	373.0	415.0	361.0	203.0
Photocurrent (μ A)	25.0	33.0	35.0	31.0	20.0

Results and Discussion

It is observed from Table 1 that there is an increase in electrical output of the cell with the increase in pH values; a maximum was obtained at pH 12.6. On further increase in pH, there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent. It was observed that the pH for the optimum condition has a relation with pK_a of the reductant and the desired pH is higher than its pK_a value ($pH > pK_a$). The reason may be the availability of reductant in its anionic form, which is a better donor form.

The electrical output of the cell was affected by the

variation of reducing agent concentration [NTA] in the system (Table 2). Lower concentration of reducing agent resulted in a fall in electrical output because fewer reducing agent molecules were available for electron-donation to dye molecules. Large concentration of reducing agent again resulted in a decrease in electrical output, because the large number of reducing agent molecules hinder the dye molecules reaching the electrode in the desired time limit.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [NTA] concentration

[Saf] = 4.00×10^{-6} M, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 12.6
Temp = 303 K

	[NTA] $\times 10^2$ M				
	1.5	1.8	2.0	2.3	2.5
Photopotential (mV)	271.0	357.0	415.0	372.0	267.0
Photocurrent (μ A)	20.0	32.0	35.0	28.0	23.0

Table 3. Effect of variation of [Safranine] concentration

[NTA] = 2.00×10^{-2} M, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 12.6,
Temp = 303 K

	[Saf] $\times 10^6$ M				
	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.2	4.5
Photopotential (mV)	310.0	385.0	415.0	368.0	295.0
Photocurrent (μ A)	13.0	31.0	35.0	26.0	12.0

Lower concentration of dye resulted into a fall in photopotential and photocurrent (Table 3) because fewer dye molecules are available for the excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode. The greater concentration of dye again resulted in a decrease in electrical output as the intensity of light reaching the dye molecule near the electrode decreases due to

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absorption of the major portion of the light by dye molecules present in path.

The effect of variation of diffusion length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameters of the cell was studied using H-cells of different dimension. The results are reported in Table 4. A sharp increase in photocurrent (i_{max}) was observed in the first few minutes of illumination and then there was a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. This photocurrent at equilibrium is represented as i_{eq} . This kind of photocurrent behaviour reveals an initial rapid reaction followed by a slow rate - determining step at a later stage. On the basis of the effect of diffusion path length on the current parameters, as investigated by Kaneko and Yamada¹, it may be concluded that the leuco or semi reduced form of dye, and the dye itself are the main electroactive species at the illuminated and the dark electrodes, respectively. However, the reducing agents and its oxidized products behave as the electron carriers in the cell diffusing through the path.

Table 4. Effect of diffusion path length (D_L)

[Saf.] = 4.00×10^{-6} M, [NTA] = 2.00×10^{-2} M, pH = 12.6,
Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , Temp. = 303 K

D_L mm	i_{max} μA	i_{eq} μA	Rate of initial generation of current $\mu\text{A min}^{-1}$
35.0	47.0	36.0	5.8
40.0	47.0	35.0	5.9
45.0	48.0	35.0	6.0
50.0	49.0	34.0	6.1
55.0	50.0	34.0	6.2

Current-voltage (i - V) characteristics of the cell was studied and the fill factor was determined as 0.37. The performance of the cell was studied by applying the external load necessary to have the current and potential at the power point after removing the source of light. It was observed that the cell can be used in the dark at its power point for 8 min.

Mechanism : On the basis of the above investigation, the mechanism of photocurrent generation in the photogalvanic cell can be represented as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

At electrode

Dark chamber :

At electrode

where Saf, Saf*, Saf⁻, R and R⁺ are the safranin, excited form of safranin, semi or leuco form of safranin, reductant (NTA) and its oxidized form, respectively.

Experimental

Safranin (Loba), NTA (Sigma) and NaOH (s.d.fine) were used. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. A mixture of the solutions of the dye, NTA, NaOH was taken in an H-shaped glass cell. A platinum electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) was dipped into one limb of the cell and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in the other and whole set was placed in dark till a stable potential was obtained. Then platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (ECE) and the limb containing the SCE was kept in dark. A water filter was placed between the exposed limb and the light source to cut off infrared radiation.

The photochemical bleaching of safranin (Saf.) was studied potentiometrically. The photopotential and photocurrent generated by the system saf./NTA/NaOH were measured by an Agronic 511 pH meter and microammeter (Sympson), respectively. The i - V characteristics of the cell were studied using an external load (log 470 K) in the circuit.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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